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“UNSHACKLED”

I tried but couldn't sleep,
My thoughts kept digging deep.
All the lies you chose to keep—
Pain now whispers, starts to creep.

I tried but couldn't breathe,
These knives I learned to unsheathe,
Yet the wounds still seethe,
I held it down beneath.

I tried but couldn't think,
Our heartbeats fell out of sync.
I tried but couldn't laugh,
Letting go should feel enough.

I tried—and finally healed.
The embers faded into scars.
All the keepsakes we concealed
Now constellate among the stars.

I tried but couldn't stop smiling
your name was just a name.
I no longer searched for your echoes,
nor traced your ghost in empty spaces.

I tried but couldn't remember your voice,
nor long for the warmth we lost.
The past unshackled its hold on me.
I stepped into the light— finally free.